

AGRICULTURE VALUE CHAIN: FEEDING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15958107>

Аннотация. Чорвачиликни ривожланишида бир қанча омиллар билан бирга чорвани йилнинг турли фаслларида сифатли озуқа билан етарлича таъминлаш ҳамда озуқа манбаларини кенгайтириш муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Бу уларни махсулдорлигини оширишга, турли касалликларга чалинишини олдини олишга, соғлом насл беришга, бутун қиймат занжири бўйлаб иштирокчилар даромадлари ўсишига ва пировардида якуний истеъмолчиларни сифатли махсулотлар билан таъминлаш имкони яратади. Ушбу мақолада чорвалик қиймат занжирининг озуқа босқичи ҳолати олиб борилган изланишлар натижаси тўғрисида фикр юритилади.

Калит сўзлар: майдо шохли чорва, чорва озуқаси, қиймат занжири.

Аннотация. В развитии животноводства, наряду с рядом факторов, важным является обеспечение скота достаточным количеством качественных кормов в разное время года и расширение источников кормов. Это позволит повысить их продуктивность, предотвратить заражение различными заболеваниями, получить здоровое потомство, увеличить доходы участников всей цепочки создания стоимости и в конечном итоге обеспечить конечных потребителей качественной продукцией. В данной статье рассматриваются результаты исследований, проведенных по состоянию кормового этапа цепочки создания стоимости в животноводстве.

Ключевые слова: мелкий рогатый скот, корм, цепочки добавленной стоимости.

Annotation. In the development of livestock farming, along with a number of factors, it is important to provide livestock with sufficient quality feed at different times of the year and expand feed sources. This will increase their productivity, prevent them from contracting various diseases, produce healthy offspring, increase the income of participants throughout the value chain, and ultimately provide end consumers with quality products. This article discusses the results of research conducted on the state of the feed stage of the livestock value chain.

Key words: small ruminants, livestock feed, value chain.

I. INTRODUCTION

Livestock is considered one of the main sources of the rural households' income and plays a significant role for food and nutrition security. Livestock farming is also considered an important source of self-employment for the rural population, especially for rural women. The sector employs about 27 percent of agricultural workers. However, it is the source of over 13 percent of the country's total greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) and most of the agricultural emissions (World Bank, 2023). A number of problems can be identified that hinder the development of the livestock value chain including: i) access to finance; ii) lack of vet system; iii) feed problems; iv) limited processing industry; v) lack of knowledge and skills in livestock farming, etc.. Areas planted with forage and feed crops have been reduced by 70% since independence, whereas the cattle population has increased by 150%, reaching 15 million head and leading to a significant increase in GHG emissions (Hoek, 2020). During the years of independence, in order to ensure the country's

food security, wheat acreage was expanded, and cotton and wheat were maintained as the main strategic commodities for many years. As a result, the area of fodder crops for livestock decreased, which also negatively affected the development of livestock farming. Although a certain amount of fodder crops were planted in the areas vacated by cotton and grain, late vegetable crops remained the main crop. Delinking livestock from cotton production has led to decreased cotton yields and reduced feed availability. Key factors constraining livestock production in Uzbekistan include insufficient feed resources and lack of land area (Hoek, 2020). Feed availability is one of the key issues of livestock rearing in Uzbekistan. Modest sizes of dehkan plots restrain provision of feeds for livestock, which is bred in dehkan households. Only 57% of households supply (even partially) their livestock with feeds produced on their own plots. The majority (75%) of them have to buy feeds (Yu.B. Yusupov et al., 2010). Moreover, 62% of households deals with collecting feeds for their livestock - mow grass, collect food waste etc. Grazing livestock along roadsides and ditches is widespread. Grazing livestock on community pastures, including by hired shepherds, is not common due to a lack of rangelands. As the population grows, the demand for livestock products, such as meat and dairy products, increases. In order to increase the efficiency of livestock farming, it is very important to increase the material and technical capabilities of farms specializing in the production of livestock feed in the regions. Cattle on the farm showed extra growth of 80.3 kg when fed a regular feed ration and 95.8 kg when fed feed supplemented with feed additives (Toshboev et al., 2024). Cattle diets were mainly based on crop residues (stover, straw) and cattle mortality due to cold stress represents a threat to animal welfare. As per conducted survey results, 43.2% of respondents would like to use more land for pasture land where 93.7% mentioned the lack of pasture land to rent (Khamdamova et al., 2024). Grazing on public pastures, including by hired herders, is not very common due to a lack of grazing land. High pressure associated with excessive number of livestock grazing, climate change and noncompliance with pasture management are main causes led to a deterioration in the quality of pastures.

II. METHODOLOGY

Field survey was conducted in Samarkand and Kashkadarya regions. Primary data is collected in value chains including farmers, livestock clusters/LLC, dehkan farms and households. Secondary data sources included National Statistics Committee and Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Data collection tools are household survey, target group interviews, expert discussions and observations, official annual reports and other relevant publications.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the survey areas, shepherds graze sheep mainly in pastures from early spring to mid-autumn. In winter sheep herders use hay and other types of fodder collected during the summer. In order to ensure the health of the sheep during the cold days of winter, they are also fed with additional concentrate feeds. Big farms use grain from their own farming while small-scale herders mainly purchase feed and grains from local feed market.

Cotton seed husk, cotton seed hulls obtained from cotton cleaning and processing plants are used as fodder for sheep. Also, cottonseed meal, sunflower meal, sesame/flax meal, peanut husks and other types of wastes from grain mills are used as additional ingredients for small ruminant feed. All types of fodder for sheep are mainly divided into three groups (Agro-Olam.Uz, 2021): i) feed made from plant products; ii) feed products made from animals; iii) mineral substances.

Green fodder. All types of plants grown naturally and artificially are considered green fodder. For example, various grasses, legumes (barley, oats, wheat) and leguminous plants (alfalfa,

chickpeas, beans), stems and leaves of root vegetables are among them. These types of fodder are mainly fed to sheep in spring, summer and autumn. In rural areas, alfalfa and corn are grown as traditional green fodder crops in households, dehkan farms and farms, while grasses are mostly harvested between trees, canal edges and rows of various vegetables. Alfalfa and corn are mainly selected and propagated by sowing seeds. In order for them to grow well, special attention and agrotechnical measures are carried out.

Roughage (rough feed) consists mainly of hay, straw and stalks of various plants (corn, cotton stalks, sorghum, sunflower and sorghum). They are widely used in livestock feeding in all regions of our country.

Local livestock feed market in Tashkent region

Hay is the most used of all types of roughage. In Uzbekistan, alfalfa hay is especially important feed for horse, sheep and cattle. Its chemical composition depends on the agrotechnical measures used in the cultivation of alfalfa, harvesting during flowering, drying and storage technology. Hay is made from the stems of all other types of plants. The chemical composition of hay varies according to its quality. For example, its composition consists of 4-26% protein, 3-7% fat, 20-35% fiber, 28-39% nitrogen-free extractives, 3-11% dust. 1 kg of quality alfalfa hay can contain up to 0.5 kg of nutrients. In addition to alfalfa, hay made from a mixture of various summer grasses, peanut hay, mosh hay, corn hay, etc. is made and fed to sheep in winter and spring.

Alfalfa bale, 20 kg

\$2.9/per bale

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Summer hay, 15 kg

\$2.0/per bale

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Peanut hay bale, 15 kg

\$2.0/per bale

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In addition, in different regions of the republic, shepherds harvest the Alhagi plant, which blooms well at the end of the summer months. Then the Alhagi is dried in the field into bales weighing 15-20 kg, and the collected bales are delivered to the place where the sheep are kept for the winter. Among the roughages, sorghum is of particular importance and contains 0.44 percent of nutrients per kilogram in its green-wet form. However, the population does not pay attention to the strength of Alhagi fodder and the fact that it grows in wide pastures, they buy straw or alfalfa from the market at an expensive price and raise sheep at home.

Autumn hay (mixed), 15 kg
\$2.3/per bale

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Alhagi bale, 15-20 kg
\$1.6/per bale

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Alhagi bales are stacked 3-4 meters high in rectangular or circular shape in open air (outside) and its top is covered with wood or tin. Due to its open sides, Alhagi attracts moisture and becomes relatively softer in rainy and cold weather. Since Alhagi grain is harvested when ripe, its red ripe grains are a useful forage that is good for sheep and goats to eat.

Straw is different from other types of plants. For example, autumn rye straw contains 35-45 percent fiber, wheat straw contains 10-20 kg of nutritional units and 0.3 kg of digestible protein per 100 kg. 4-5% of protein is contained in the straw of grain plants, 6-7% in the straw of leguminous plants. It also contains a small amount of carotene, calcium and phosphorus. Therefore, the nutritional value of straw is low, and it is relatively difficult to digest it.

Liquid content feeds. They mainly include root crops, potatoes, legumes, silage, haylage, beetroot and green grass. Without the green grass, the wet feed is low in protein and minerals. Among them, potato tuber is the most nutritious. Because 1 kg of potato nodule is equivalent to 0.3 kg of nutritional unit. If chopped tubers (diameter 3 cm) are mixed with fodder or chopped hay, haylage, straw then animals will eat them with appetite and feed waste will be less.

Fortified (concentrate) feed. Chemically enriched feed is extremely nutritious and rich in various substances. The feed is low in water and fiber. Plant grain and grain processing wastes are also included in feed. The nutritional value of 1 kg of feed is equal to 1 nutritional unit, sometimes even more. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, barley, corn and sorghum feed is used for sheep. The fodder contains a lot of phosphorus and little calcium, and 1 kg of fodder contains 78-80 g of protein. Although the content of *bran* is second only to whole grain, it is rich in protein and phosphorus.

Mix concentrate feeds in local market

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Cottonseed meal in local feed market

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Millcake and powdered millcake are valuable for cattle and sheep due to their high protein content (300-370 g per 1 kg) and their nutritional value. Millcake keeps animals full, increases the creaminess of cows' milk. However, it contains a small amount of a harmful substance called gossypol. Therefore, it is harmful to give large quantities of millcake to cattle without any other ingredients. When using concentrate feeds, it is useful to give them to cattle as mixed feed.

Silage is made from freshly harvested or dried, crushed plant mass. 10-20% of chopped straw is added to silage mass with a moisture content of more than 75%. The goal of making silage is to conserve the digestible fiber, protein, and energy in the forage, to preserve forage nutrients for feeding at a later date and to maintain the protein in a form that can be utilized efficiently by the ruminant animal. This is accomplished by the conversion (by fermentation) of plant sugars to organic acids. Well fermented silages result in reduced dry matter losses, in more feed being available for feeding dairy cows and small ruminants.

The process of reaping corn for silage

The cost of combine harvesting of 1 ha of land is 1.0 mln UZS (\$81.0). 70-80 tons of green mass is obtained for silage from 1 ha. The price of selling 1 trailer (4.5 tons) of green mass is 1,5 mln UZS (\$121.0).

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Hydroponics (greenfeed) and Granule (pills) feed. Due to factors such as climate change, limited water resources, lack of fodder base for sheep and goats, low quality of fodder, dwindling pastures, high prices of fodder, hydroponics, which is environmentally safe, high-quality, cheap and resource-efficient fodder cultivation, is increasing. Sheep and goat breeders are also very interested in it. *Granule (pills) feed* has a number of advantages in sheep feeding, including: uniform distribution of various feed raw materials and additives (vitamins) in the feed, reduction of feed waste by spilling from feed containers, convenience of feed for sheep consumption, ease of transportation and distribution of feed, granule lack of storage space for feed, etc.

Greenfeed growing in hydroponic method

Pellet feed for sheep fed for meat

COST COMPARISON OF GREEN FEED AND TRADITIONAL FEEDS

	Green feed*	Wheat bran	Corn bran	Dried alfalfa hay**	Wheat straw***
Cost (UZS/ton)	2,000,000 (\$162)	3,200,000 (\$260)	3,800 000 (\$310)	2,400,000 (\$195)	1,500,000 (\$122)
Daily consumption per sheep, kg	3.0	2.5	2.5	7.0	7.0
Daily cost per sheep, UZS	6,000 (\$0.48)	8,000 (\$0.65)	9,500 (\$0.78)	16,800 (\$1.36)	10,500 (\$0.85)
Digestibility	High	Good	Good	Medium	Low
Productivity (weight gain/day)****	High	High	High	Medium	Very Low

* Selling price;

**One bale of dried alfalfa is 15 kg and price is UZS 35,000.0 /bale.

***Average weight of one bale of wheat straw is 10 kg and rice is UZS 18,000.0/bale.

****based on survey data and interviews with key informants

Source: survey field data

Sheep raised for meat production must first be gutted and trained to consume more feed. That is, feeding large amounts of feed at once to fed young sheep will cause them to choke and lose their appetite. If they are gradually trained to eat more concentrates and green forages, they will gain weight faster and their appetites will be balanced. For example, to a newly purchased sheep with a live weight of 40 kg for meat feeding: 3 times 250 grams of bran every 8 hours for the 1st 10 days; 250 grams every 6 hours in the 2nd 10 days. During this period, the sheep gradually learns to eat more feed and learns to rest after eating enough. After that, it is possible to fill the sheep's feeder with fodder and switch to continuous feeding mode. As sheep get fatter, they begin to eat less feed (their stomachs get smaller). This method ensures that they fatten evenly and quickly, reduces various costs and accelerates the time of sending to slaughter.

List of the requirements and availability of coarse and green feed for farms that specialized in breeding livestock, thous.tons

Feed types	Demand, target	Actual	Coverage %
<i>Hay</i>	515.0	350.9	68%
<i>Straw</i>	487.0	1491.2	306%
<i>Senage</i>	695.0	389.5	56%
<i>Silage</i>	949.0	580.9	64%
<i>Beet</i>	228.0	0.3	0.15%
<i>Green mass</i>	3937.2	1594.5	47%
Total feed	6607.2	4491.0	67%

Source: Adopted from Toshboev et al., 2024

During the survey, it was found that only 10% of sheep herders (mainly farms and dehkan farms) grow plants that they use for feed preparation and stocking for winter on their land. The survey did not explore the factors preventing this in depth. On the contrary, the reasons for this have been thoroughly studied in literature review.

Reasons restraining dehkans, households and farms in producing feed crops

Source: adopted from Yusupov et al, 2010.

In 2023, the productivity of grain and leguminous crops, which are widely used in the cultivation of livestock feed, was 4.2 tons per hectare, while that of wheat was equal to 4.5 tons per hectare.

Productivity of selected crops in 2023, in centner*

*Centner equals to 100 kg

Source: collected from <https://data.egov.uz>

Payment for grazing. Farms hire shepherds to graze their sheep on leased pastures and pay 3,000.0 UZS per month per sheep. Pasture rent farmers pay 110,000.0 UZS per year for 1 sheep (grazing period for 9 months). Households and dehkan farms (with a small number of sheep) pay 15,000.0 UZS per month for pasture rent per sheep, depending on their location in different areas. In the summer months, sheep rest in the pasture for 3-4 hours during the day. At this time they are also watered. At night, it is fully grazed and free-fed. Also, the fields where cotton, corn, wheat, barley, mung beans (mush), melons, and other types of crops are harvested for sheep feeding are also rented.

Challenges related to feed and feeding

During the survey, 75% sheep breeders reported that the number of sheep they own decreased in the last 3 years, about 3% reported that the number did not change, and the remaining 22% reported that the number of sheep increased. The reasons why the number of sheep decreased or did not change were studied and it was found that various factors influence this.

Factors hindering the increase in the number of sheep

Factors	Decreased	Constant	Increase
	75%	3%	22%
Financial issues	A	A	C
Lack of feed and pasture	A	A	A
Lack of sheep housing in winter	C	B	D
Lack of time	D	D	D
Other	High cost, Low margin	Selling issues, Diseases	Diseases

Factors' effect level: A-strong, B-Moderate, C-Low, D-No effect

Source: Survey data

There are a number of fodder-related problems, such as poor pasture quality and fodder sources, interruptions in fodder supply, shortage of fodder products in different seasons, high cost of fodder products (especially in winter), and lack of quality nutritious crop planting practices across the country. The salinity level is increasing in the land areas where food and other main agricultural crops are grown. As a result, this is an obstacle to increasing the land area for planting nutritious crops for livestock. It is becoming difficult to feed small ruminants in the desert and sub-mountain regions with the decrease in the quality of the pastures.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

- selection of suitable varieties and rapid reproduction of their seeds, taking into account the climatic conditions of pastures;
- identifying and restoring pastures in crisis and planting desert nutritious crops to increase their productivity;
- supply of seeds of nutritious crops based on the demand of farms specializing in sheep breeding.
- to further reduce GHG emissions
- considering options for rotations or intercropping of food and cash crops with forages, and more adequate and strategic use of higher-cost agroindustrial by-products.
- ensure the production and availability of seedlings of (leguminous) forage trees for silvopastoral systems by establishing regional and local nurseries.
- introduction of non-traditional annual forage crops such as sorghum, triticale, barley and oats, and perennial legume forage crops such as alfalfa and aspartame (supplemented with corn as feed);
- introduction of the concept of determining the types of fodder in summer and winter pastures, as well as their productivity, alternating grazing, planting and restoration of pastures;
- training of farmers and representatives of local non-governmental nongovernmental organizations on sheep and goat keeping, feeding, medical services, fodder cultivation and storage methods;
- introduction of new methods (for food production) such as aquaponics and hydroponics, which should be developed and promoted throughout the country.

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